

Chemical and biological activity of peats

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The search for new raw materials of biologically active substances (**BAS**) of natural origin is an urgent task for the modern period. In this regard, peat is a relatively cheap and practically unlimited raw material base. However, the range of peat properties is quite wide and depends on the conditions of swamp formation, the depth of peat occurrence, and its botanical composition. Therefore, it is important to correctly select the necessary raw material base with specific requirements for the quality of peat and its reserves for the required products. The aim of the work was to study the composition of organic matter (**OM**), nitrogen peat, their enzymological activity, determine the correlation links between them and substantiate the criteria for the evaluation scale of the properties of eutrophic peat when choosing a raw material base for the production of BAS.

In the territory of Western Siberia, within the taiga and subtaiga regions, 140 samples of eutrophic peat belonging to 12 groups were selected. Each species of peat is represented of 6–19 samples, in which the botanical composition, degree of decomposition, ash content, fractional composition of nitrogen and organic matter, enzyme and microbiology activity were determined.

The following results were obtained. The content of humic acids (**HA**) in eutrophic peats increased in the following order: grass-moss – moss – wood – wood-grass, grass group. Peat groups differed significantly in the content of the HA-1 fraction. The moss group of peat stood out in particular with a low content of total nitrogen, its non-hydrolyzable fraction and a high content of easily hydrolyzable nitrogen, which determined the high mobility of nitrogen compounds. Among all the studied characteristics of the composition of peat OM, according to the correlation analysis, the following indicators are reliable: the sum of HA, lipids, carbohydrates and C:N ratio. This gives grounds to consider them as possible parameters for compiling an evaluation scale for selecting peats for the production of BAS.

A study of the enzymological and biological properties of eutrophic peats has established that an increase in the activity of invertase, protease, nitrate- and nitrite reductase, and polyphenoloxidase can be traced in the order: woody – woody-grass–grass. The calculation of the correlation coefficients between enzyme activity and parameters of other properties of eutrophic peats revealed that the greatest number of correlations were observed with fractions of peat OM and nitrogen, and to a lesser extent (r less than 0.7) with protease, nitrite reductase, peroxidase and parameters of microbiological properties of peats. In the process of analyzing correlation links, it was revealed that total and enzymatic catalase, polyphenoloxidase, and invertase can be controlling parameters of the enzymological state of eutrophic peats.

General conclusion: significant parameters of the evaluation scale of the properties of eutrophic peat for substantiating the choice of raw materials for the production of BAS are individual fractions of organic matter and nitrogen, total and enzymatic catalase, polyphenol oxidase, and invertase.

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